

The Effect of Using Social Media on Job Satisfaction: Is There A Role for Job Engagement and Organization Engagement As a Mediator?

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine how the influence of the use of social media (Work-related social media use) and social media (Social-related social media use) on job satisfaction. In addition, to find out how the role of work engagement and organizational engagement, as a mediating variable in the relationship. The research was conducted in Indonesia with the analysis unit of the State Civil Servant (SCS) domiciled in Banda Aceh and Aceh Besar. A sample of 212 respondents obtained by using a questionnaire distribution technique using google form, data analysis using SEM-AMOS. The results of the analysis show that the use of social media (Work-related social media use) has no effect on job satisfaction, but the use of social media (Social-related social media use) is found to increase the job satisfaction of SCS. The results of the analysis also show that the use of social media (Work-related social media use) can increase work engagement, but has no effect on increasing organizational engagement. The use of social media (Social-related social media use) contributes to an increase in work engagement and organizational engagement. Furthermore, it was found that there was a significant effect of work engagement and organizational engagement on SCS job satisfaction. Work engagement and organizational engagement play a role as a mediating variable (partially) in the relationship between social media use (Social-related social media use) and job satisfaction. But there is no role as a mediating variable in the relationship between (Work-related social media use) and job satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Social media, job engagement, organization engagement, job satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of technology has triggered the development of means of communication. One of the fastest growing means of communication is social media. Aral's research (2013) writes that technological innovations such as social media have facilitated communication and brought many benefits such as improving innovation, knowledge sharing, and collaboration (Ali-Hassan, et al 2015). Social media is used in virtual communities so that people can easily create, share, and exchange information. Hence, no wonder nowadays social media has changed the way humans communicate, collaborate and consume (Ali-Hassan et al., 2015). Demircioglu's research (2018) writes many government employees have started using social media for work purposes.

The use of social media in the work environment is most closely related in sharing information about work and building social relationships between employees. Thus the use of social media in the work environment is divided into use for work-related social media usage and social-related social media usage (Zhang et al., 2019). In the use of work-related, companies use social media to communicate with their employees such as planning meetings, asking for work, or sharing information about policies and procedures. As for social-related, employees communicate with other co-workers such as planning events, sharing hobbies, and others (Zhang et al., 2019). In general, the use of work-related and social-related social media usage provides easy access to information so that communication is more efficient, and it will lead to improvements in employee engagement (Gonzalez et al., 2013).

Employee engagement is the feeling of employee attachment with the company and their work. Kahn (1990) defines employee engagement as a way of expressing themselves emotionally, physically, and cognitively (Men et al., 2020). There are several dimensions to measure employee engagement, but according to Zhang (2019) the most influential aspects of employee engagement in the company are the aspects of job engagement and organization engagement. Job engagement is a feeling of an employee feeling attached to their job, while organization engagement is how an employee feels attached to where they work and dedicates their life in the company. Based on Zhang's research (2019) these two things have a positive effect as mediation of the use of social media on employee's job satisfaction. Job satisfaction according to Locke (1976) is a pleasant emotional state of

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how workers view their work (Demircioglu, 2018). Job satisfaction is also an expectation to successfully complete the task in every situation (Mahdani & Adam, 2017).

The State Civil Servant (SCS) or government employee is known to use social media a lot. This has been reviewed for a long time and there are already regulations governing it. Minister of Empowerment of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia issued regulation number 83 of 2012 on Guidelines Utilization of Social Media Government Agencies. In the rule mentioned social media as a means of communication to do work such as content management and communication media planning. Based on pre-survey research on 30 SCS in Banda Aceh as the capital of Aceh province, it is known that many SCS uses social media for work and social purposes.

Although the use of social media has expanded, research about understanding of social media still very limited (Mergel, 2017; Song & Lee, 2016), particularly the effect of social media on the job satisfaction of government employees. We need to understand the importance of employee's job satisfaction from various sides, including the use of social media that has been widely used by SCS. Nevertheless, job satisfaction in terms of the use of social media has not been proven empirically. Despite the existence of technologies to accelerate and facilitate the work, human resources still has an important role because even though the equipment is extremely contemporary, if SCS could not perform their duties with interest and joy then the company will not achieve as many result as it can actually be achieved (Nasution & Said M, 2018).

However, so far, the average research in improving job satisfaction in Banda Aceh has only focused on job satisfaction reviewed from salary, supervision, commitment, and leadership style (Lubis, 2020; Muhandani, 2019; Hasnah, 2018; Rafiie, 2017; Wahyudi, 2017; Hatta, 2017). Moreover, research on social media use generally focuses on the use of social media reviewed in terms of positive and negative usage (Fusi & Feeney, 2018; Kühnel et al., 2020; Liu & Bakici, 2019; Setiadi, 2016; Tajudeen et al., 2018) or frequency of use in company (Panjaitan & Prasetya, 2017; Novialumi, 2019), while the effect of the use of social media on SCS's job satisfaction, especially in Banda Aceh as the capital of Aceh province is not yet discovered and also, there is no empirical proven about it. In fact, the use of social media by SCS in Banda Aceh has been widespread and could affect employee's job satisfaction. Therefore, the author will examine the influence of social media use on job satisfaction with two dimensions of employee engagement, such as job engagement and organization engagement as mediation variables.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Robbins (2017) defines job satisfaction as a common perceived someone's attitude toward work. Keith Davis (2011) states that job satisfaction is a feeling that support employee's experience while working. Based on the expert's opinions above, job satisfaction is a feeling of how people view their work along with factors that support or do not support them. Employees will be satisfied in their work if aspects of the work and for themselves are support and otherwise when such aspects do not support, the employee will not be satisfied in the work.

To improve job satisfaction, one of the way is increase employee engagement. This has also been researched by Rachman et al (2016), the results of his research showed employee engagement positively affects job satisfaction and increases employee productivity. Research by Men et al (2020), Zhang et al (2019) and Parveen et al (2015) proves that the two dimensions of employee engagement, such as job engagement and organization engagement, could increase when employees use social media for work-related and social-related, because it is considered more transparent so it increases trust and employees bound. Job engagement or work attachment, according to Kahn's (1990), is described as a multidimensional concept of motivation that reflects a person's simultaneous physical, cognitive, and emotional investment while working (Kahn W, 1990). Organization engagement according to Job (2017) is the extent employees are psychologically present in certain organizational roles. One way for employees to contribute to the company can be seen through organization engagement or employee attachment with the company.

Zoonen in its research (van Zoonen et al., 2014), found the use of social relates positively to employee engagement through improved accessibility and efficient communication. The use of social media in the work environment is most closely related in sharing information about work and building social relationships between employees. Thus the use of social media in the work environment is divided into use for work-related social media usage and social-related social media usage (Zhang et al., 2019). Use of social media for work purposes such as scheduling meetings, discussing work projects and sharing information on company policies and procedures (Zhang et al., 2019).

Yingjie (2019) explained motivation to use social media for work, employees believe social media facilitates internal communication and helps them obtain, share, transfer information and knowledge related to the company. The use of social-related social media usage is defined as building close relationships between co-workers, finding co-workers who have similar interests, planning to spent time together, and having fun. This brings good bonds between co-workers (Yingjie et al., 2019). Social

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media makes a strengthen relationships with co-workers (Schmidt et al., 2016). From the results of literature review, then we formed a research framework and hypothesis below:

Figure 1. Research Framework

Hypothesis

- H1: Work-related social media usage influences job satisfaction
- H2: Social-related social media usage influences job satisfaction
- H3: Work-related social media usage influences on job engagement
- H4: Work-related social media usage influences on organization engagement
- H5: Social-related social media usage influences on job engagement
- H6: Social-related social media usage influences on organization engagement
- H7: Job engagement influences on job satisfaction
- H8: Organization engagement influences on job satisfaction
- H9: Job engagement mediates the relationship between work-related social media use and job satisfaction
- H10: Organization engagement mediates the relationship between work-related social media use and job satisfaction
- H11: Job engagement mediates the relationship between Social-related social media use and job satisfaction
- H12: Organization engagement mediates the relationship between Social-related social media use and job satisfaction

METHODS

Sample and Data

The research will be conducted in Banda Aceh and Aceh Besar. The data and information used in this study will be obtained from the dissemination of online questionnaires. Questionnaires will be given to state civil servants (SCS) who is working in Banda Aceh. Furthermore, the object will be associated with five variables that include work-related social media usage, social-related social media usage, job engagement, organization engagement, and job satisfaction.

Measurement and Data Analysis

There are two section to measure data. First section, respondents must answer about personal demographic data by choosing the most suits answer to the respondent conditions. Second sections, Likert scale is used to measure perceptions' of each questions. The Likert scale is used to translate a measured variable into a variable indicator. Then the indicator is used as a starting point to arrange the items of the instrument that can be a statement or question. Furthermore, data were analyzed using The Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with AMOS 22.0 statistics software package.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 show the characteristic of respondents. The respondent's characteristic is the respondent's profile when taking the data.

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondent

No.	Descriptions	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Gender		
	Men	86	40,6
	Women	126	59,4

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Amount		212	100,0
2.	Age		
	18-29 years	85	40,1
	30-39 years	70	33,0
	40-49 years	30	14,2
	>50 years	27	12,7
Amount		212	100,0
3.	Last Education		
	Senior High School	0	0
	Graduated Diploma	27	12,7
	Bachelor (S1)	160	75,5
	Master (S2)	20	9,4
	Master (S3)	5	2,4
Amount		212	100,0
4.	Employee Status		
	PNS	160	75,5
	PPPK	52	24,5
Amount		212	100,0
5.	Frequently Used Social Media		
	WhatsApp	189	89,1
	Line	1	0,5
	Instagram	19	9,0
	Telegram	3	1,4
Amount		212	100,0

In table 2 the authors show the results of validity testing which is conducted using convergent validity. This test is to see if the indicators describe the construct to be analyzed. Indicators whose estimated value > 0.50 will serve as constructive indicators. Which show all the indicators are valid.

Table 2. Results of Validity Test

Variable Indicators	<i>Loading Factor</i>	Decision
A1 ← Work-Related Social Media	0,697	Valid
A2 ← Work-Related Social Media	0,798	Valid
A3 ← Work-Related Social Media	0,835	Valid
A4 ← Work-Related Social Media	0,699	Valid
B1 ← Social-Related Social Media	0,723	Valid
B2 ← Social-Related Social Media	0,763	Valid
B3 ← Social-Related Social Media	0,747	Valid
B4 ← Social-Related Social Media	0,709	Valid
C1 ← Job Engagement	0,635	Valid
C2 ← Job Engagement	0,734	Valid
C3 ← Job Engagement	0,705	Valid
C4 ← Job Engagement	0,615	Valid
C5 ← Job Engagement	0,655	Valid
D1 ← Organization Engagement	0,703	Valid
D2 ← Organization Engagement	0,803	Valid
D3 ← Organization Engagement	0,761	Valid
D4 ← Organization Engagement	0,621	Valid

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D5 ← Organization Engagement	0,781	Valid
E1 ← Job Satisfaction	0,762	Valid
E2 ← Job Satisfaction	0,785	Valid
E3 ← Job Satisfaction	0,800	Valid

Table 3 is the result of the reliability test. From the test results show the value Construct of Reliability is larger than 0.70, which shows all the variables studied are reliable.

Table 3. Results of Reliability Test

Item	Std. Loading	Total Loading	e.j	(Σ Std. Loading) ²	(Σ Std. Loading) ² +e.j	CR	Decisions
A1	0,697	3,029	1,692	9,175	10,866	0,844	Reliable
A2	0,798						
A3	0,835						
A4	0,699						
B1	0,723	2,942	1,834	8,655	10,490	0,825	Reliable
B2	0,763						
B3	0,747						
B4	0,709						
C1	0,635	3,344	2,754	11,182	13,936	0,802	Reliable
C2	0,734						
C3	0,705						
C4	0,615						
C5	0,655						
D1	0,703	3,669	2,286	13,462	15,748	0,855	Reliable
D2	0,803						
D3	0,761						
D4	0,621						
D5	0,781						
E1	0,762	2,347	1,163	5,508	6,672	0,826	Reliable
E2	0,785						
E3	0,800						

Figure 2 shows the correlation test results between constructs. To obtain Goodness-of-fit on CFA correlation modeling, we need to eliminate some indicators that has modification indices value more than 10000 and this is final results. The figure shown the CFA is good.

Figure 2. The results of testing the influence between variables and the effect of mediation variables through CFA Goodness-of-fit

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Table 4 shows the results of testing the influence between variables. Hypothesis testing is directly seen in probability values, CR values must be greater than 1.96 and P less than 0.05. If the criteria is capable, then the hypothesis can be accepted. It shows one hypothesis in this way work-related social media usage toward job satisfaction does not meet the criteria, so it can not be accepted.

Table 4. Result of testing effect between constructs

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
KK	<---	MSHK	0,109	0,100	1,013	0,311
KK	<---	MSHS	0,904	0,163	5,088	***
JE	<---	MSHK	0,238	0,082	2,200	0,028
OE	<---	MSHK	0,268	0,091	2,591	0,010
JE	<---	MSHS	0,815	0,099	6,190	***
OE	<---	MSHS	0,297	0,090	2,855	0,004
KK	<---	JE	0,294	0,154	2,340	0,019
KK	<---	OE	0,200	0,083	2,539	0,011

*** significantly different from zero at the 0,001 level (two-tailed).

Table 5 and table 6 shows the results of the mediation effect test (job engagement and organization engagement) on the work-related social media usage and social-related social media usage toward job satisfaction. Based on the test results, work-related social media usage and social-related social media usage through job engagement is 23,9% and 6,9%. Meanwhile, through organization engagement is 5,9% and 5,3%.

Table 5. Results of mediation effect testing through job engagement

	Indirect Effect Through JE			
	MSHS	MSHK	JE	KK
JE	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
KK	0,239	0,069	0,000	0,000

Table 6. Results of mediation effect testing through organization engagement

	Indirect Effect Through OE			
	MSHS	MSHK	OE	KK
OE	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
KK	0,059	0,053	0,000	0,000

This study focuses on the social media usage which is divided work-related and social-related to job satisfaction with two dimensions of employee engagement in this way job engagement and organization engagement as mediations. From the results of data analysis, we have found that there is a strong influence between social-related social media usage toward job satisfaction, these findings are consistent with Brett (2016) who states that the use social-related social media between workers has a significant influence on job satisfaction. But work-related social media usage has no effect toward job satisfaction. Demircioglu (2018) in his research found similar issues in different context, his research found that the use of social media by public service employees had no direct effect on job satisfaction. The results of this study are also supported based on a statement in Schmidt's research (2015) in which connections between colleagues through social media have no indication to help employees in work engagement.

Subsequently, work-related social media has an effect to organization engagement and job engagement. But as we can see in the table the effect to organization engagement is greater than job engagement. This is supported by a statement in Zhang's research (2019) in which job engagement is a stronger predictor than organization engagement because job engagement reflects employee inputs on the job. So when using social media to plan meetings or share policies and procedures does not affect how employees feel very engaged to their work.

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Furthermore, social-related social media usage has a significant effect on job engagement and organization engagement, these findings are consistent with Zhang's research (2019), social-related social media usage has a positive and significant effect on organization engagement and job engagement. As in Men's research, suggests that the more employees read uploads from companies and coworkers, interact with content by liking, sharing, and commenting on posts, and engaging in one-on-one group conversations or discussions on social media, the more they feel engrossed, attentive, dedicated, connected, and engaged in the organization (Men et al., 2020).

Afterward, job engagement and organization engagement has a significant effect on job satisfaction. The results of this study are consistent with Rahman (2016) in which job engagement directly affects job satisfaction. In additions, Job (2017) states that organization engagement is one of the significant predictors of job satisfaction. We also found, there is a partial mediates effect but not so strong between work-related and social-related social media usage toward job satisfaction through job engagement and organization engagement. This indicates that the influence social media usage has more influence on job satisfaction directly not through mediation.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concluded that the social-related social media usage affects SCS's job satisfaction in Banda Aceh. This means that if the company wants to increase the job satisfaction of SCS in Banda Aceh, it can increase the use of social media from social-related because it will contribute to the increase in employee attachment and then increase job satisfaction. As we can seen above, the work-related social media usage has no direct effect to SCS's job satisfaction in Banda Aceh. Other researchers can add more possible factors to affects job satisfaction.

Researchers can also expand the scope of media social usesage not just in government company. Other researchers can conduct research again by considering other possible indicators. The final suggestion that the author can give to government agencies in Banda Aceh is that this study can be used as one of the considerations to improve SCS's job satisfaction in Banda Aceh with the work-related and social-related social media usage.

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